

Uncertainty Quantification of a Ductile Damage Evolution Model in an Adhesively Bonded Single Lap Shear Joint

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SwRI Overview

- Founded in 1947
- Nonprofit organization
- More than 3,100 employees
- More than 1,500 acres / 6.1 km² facility in San Antonio, TX
- More than 2.5 million ft² / 232,000 m² of laboratories, workshops & offices
- More than 1,500 patents
- 52 R&D 100 awards
- Deep sea to deep space

Motivation

- **Bonded composite** structures are increasingly favored for their potential to reduce weight and improve structural efficiency
- Complex behavior of adhesive joints under varying load conditions necessitates **predictive modeling** approaches that can accurately simulate failure mechanisms
- This study applies the **Ductile Damage Evolution Material (DDEM)** model to single lap shear joints to predict strength and time to failure under shear loading

Previous Research: Simulation

- Single Lap Shear Joint (SLSJ)

Single Lap Shear Joint Dimensions	
Parameter	Value (mm)
t_m	3.18
t_a	1.00
t_b	4.18
L_0	61.10
L_a	150.00
L_{bl}	25.40
L_{ext}	60.00
w	25.40
θ	45°

Previous Research: Material Characterization

- Adherend and adhesive tensile tests

Previous Research: Experimental Results

- SLSJ Strength
- Time-to-failure
- Simulation prediction
 - Pretty good strength
 - Terrible time-to-failure
- Initial conclusion was to investigate the effect of the adherend response

VVUQ Approach

- Parameterize model
- Establish PIRT
- Identify sensitive parameters
- Build surrogate model
- Global Sensitivity Analysis
- Bayesian Model Calibration

PIRT

- Phenomena (Parameter) Identification Ranking Table
- Engineering judgement
- Quantify parameter uncertainties

Parameter	Symbol	Nominal Value	Variance	Deviation	Distribution	Low	High	Importance	Confidence
Geometry									
Specimen Width	W	0.02540	5%	0.00127	Triangular				
Overlap Length (Adhesive Length)	L_a	0.05000	50%	0.02500	Uniform	0.025	0.075		
Adhesive Thickness	t_a	0.00100	20%	0.00020	Triangular	0.00080	0.00120		
Adhesive Flash Angle	theta	60.0	10%	6.00000	Normal	42	78		
Fixed Adherend Length	L_ae	0.15000	5%	0.00750	Triangular				
Fixed Adherend Thickness	t_ae	0.003175	5%	0.00016	Triangular				
Load Adherend Length	L_al	0.15000	5%	0.00750	Triangular				
Load Adherend Thickness	t_al	0.003175	5%	0.00016	Triangular				
Fixed Block Length	L_be	0.02540	5%	0.00127	Triangular				
Fixed Block Thickness	t_be	t_al + t_a							
Load Block Length	L_bl	0.02540	5%	0.00127	Triangular				
Load Block Thickness	t_bl	t_ae + t_a							
Adherend Material Properties									
Modulus of Elasticity	E_b	7.104E+10	8%	5.918E+09	Normal	53287104000	88792896000		
Poisson's Ratio	nu_b	0.31	5%	0.0155	Normal				
Density	rho_b	2650.0	5%	132.5	Normal				
Yield Strength	Sy_b	186000000	4%	7626000	Normal	163122000	208878000		
Mod Ram. Osg. Power Term	n_b	5.7	3%	0.14	Normal	5.310	6.171		
Adhesive Material Properties									
Modulus of Elasticity	E_a	2.060E+09	4%	7.828E+07	Normal	1825160000	2294840000		
Poisson's Ratio	nu_a	0.40	5%	0.02	Normal				
Density	rho_a	1218.0	5%	60.9	Normal				
Yield Strength	Sy_a	283000000.0	5%	1386700	Normal	24139900	32460100		
Ram. Osg. Power Term	n_a	11.6	7%	0.85	Normal	9.035	14.165		
Fracture Strain	fs_a	0.03169	9%	0.00273	Normal				
Stress Triaxiality	st_a	-0.130	10%	-0.013	Normal				
Strain Rate	sr_a	4.33E-04	10%	4.33E-05	Normal				
Damage Reduction	dr_a	1.29E-03	17%	2.19E-04	Normal				
Damage Displacement	dd_a	1.63E-05	36%	5.87E-06	Normal	0.00000456	0.00002804		
Loading									
Crosshead Rate	velocity	2.167E-05	1%	2.17E-07	Normal				
Load Ramp		Tabular			Deterministic				
Solver Parameters									
Time Period		1050			Deterministic				
Time Points		Tabular			Deterministic				
Mass Scaling		0.01			Deterministic				
Adherend Mesh Density	mesh_adherends	0.001			Deterministic				
Adhesive Mesh Density	mesh_adhesive	0.0001			Deterministic				

Deterministic Sensitivity Study

- Central differencing of nominal parameters with a standard deviation of $1 \cdot \sigma$
- Used to identify highest sensitivities
- Down select parameters for next steps
- Adhesive angle identified

Adhesive Angle Measurement

- Using an optical microscope, the adhesive fillet angles were measured
- Previous assumption was 45 degrees
- Angle was measured closer to 30 degrees

Surrogate Model

- Response Surface created using NESSUS RST
- Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) used to generate domain of inputs
- Uniform distribution $\pm 3\sigma$
- Typically use 10*variables simulations
- 5% of simulations failed in the adherend, removed from training data
- Gaussian Process Model
- LOO cross-validation

Global Sensitivity Analysis

- Monte Carlo: 100,000 samples
- Sobol indices
- Time-to-failure effects
 - Damage Evolution
 - Adhesive Angle
 - Adhesive Yield Stress
- SLSJ Strength
 - Damage Evolution
 - Overlap Length
 - Adherend Yield Stress

Bayesian Calibration

- Goals
 - Obtain a set of likely model parameters that predicts the two responses of the SLSJ model
 - Capture uncertainty in calibration parameters due to limited data
- Down-selected calibration parameters based on sensitivity analysis
- Used uniform prior distributions
- Likelihood function:

$$L(\theta) = L_{SLSJ,S_{max}}(\theta) \cdot L_{SLSJ,T_{failure}}(\theta)$$

$$L_{SLSJ,S_{max}}(\theta) = \prod \text{NormPDF}(GP_{SLSJ,S_{max}}(\theta) - SLSJ_{S_{max},i}, \sigma_{SLSJ,S_{max}})$$

- Strength & time-to-failure within 5% of the test data

Validation Testing

- Overlap length (30, 60, 75)
- Fillet angle (30, 45, 60)
- FEM accuracy:
 - 7% for strength
 - 17% for time
- NESSUS surrogate model
 - 12% for strength
 - 19% for time

Serial Number	Specimen Geometry		NESSUS RST		FEA		Test Results		Strength Error (%)		Time Error (%)	
	Overlap Length	Fillet Angle	Load	Time	Load	Time	Load	Time	FEA	NESSUS	FEA	NESSUS
SLSJ-25-30-001	0.02881	33.0	21211	264.7	18855	309.6	15200	253.0	24.0	39.5	22.4	4.6
SLSJ-25-30-002	0.02778	37.6	20036	238.2	18010	279.2	15214	226.0	18.4	31.7	23.5	5.4
SLSJ-25-30-003	0.02408	32.0	17801	270.7	16741	248.2	14752	220.0	13.5	20.7	12.8	23.0
SLSJ-25-45-001	0.02731	36.5	19800	244.4	17915	275.8	16822	244.0	6.5	17.7	13.0	0.2
SLSJ-25-45-002	0.02507	37.2	18119	240.5	16898	246.8	15353	273.0	10.1	18.0	9.6	11.9
SLSJ-25-45-003	0.02663	42.6	18761	211.5	17085	250.0	15862	210.0	7.7	18.3	19.0	0.7
SLSJ-25-60-001	0.03153	45.9	21842	195.3	18775	305.0	17398	302.0	7.9	25.5	1.0	35.3
SLSJ-25-60-002	0.03001	49.4	20412	179.5	17727	269.2	18024	252.0	1.6	13.3	6.8	28.8
SLSJ-25-60-003	0.02783	46.2	19251	193.9	17456	254.8	17676	296.0	1.2	8.9	13.9	34.5
SLSJ-60-30-001	0.06533	34.8	25626	497.5	23959	567.4	21669	345.6	10.6	18.3	64.2	44.0
SLSJ-60-30-002	0.07306	31.0	28950	513.8	23956	519.4	20711	438.9	15.7	39.8	18.3	17.1
SLSJ-60-30-003	0.05975	34.5	23467	498.9	23599	557.8	22195	475.0	6.3	5.7	17.4	5.0
SLSJ-60-30-004	0.06100	42.9	24187	543.3	23208	525.0	21153	409.5	9.7	14.3	28.2	32.7
SLSJ-60-45-001	0.06264	42.4	23333	457.6	22900	481.0	23593	500.0	2.9	1.1	3.8	8.5
SLSJ-60-45-002	0.05943	31.5	23519	511.8	23847	587.6	22589	450.0	5.6	4.1	30.6	13.7
SLSJ-60-45-003	0.07387	38.6	26099	480.9	23104	441.4	24405	682.0	5.3	6.9	35.3	29.5
SLSJ-60-60-001	0.06156	51.6	22762	409.9	22136	456.2	24521	518.0	9.7	7.2	11.9	20.9
SLSJ-60-60-002	0.05868	39.0	22739	477.5	23154	515.2	24756	750.0	6.5	8.1	31.3	36.3
SLSJ-60-60-003	0.06352	55.9	23042	385.9	22046	437.0	23400	480.0	5.8	1.5	9.0	19.6
SLSJ-75-30-001	0.07482	28.6	23718	456.4	24233	536.0	24889	585.0	2.6	4.7	8.4	22.0
SLSJ-75-30-002	0.07354	30.6	23275	450.7	23802	499.0	22319	441.0	6.6	4.3	13.2	2.2
SLSJ-75-30-003	0.07295	32.1	23070	446.5	23244	454.0	22668	606.0	2.5	1.8	25.1	26.3
SLSJ-75-45-001	0.06936	44.2	21675	412.9	23172	471.8	23215	508.0	0.2	6.6	7.1	18.7
SLSJ-75-45-002	0.07246	38.4	22789	428.9	23264	461.0	24422	474.0	4.7	6.7	2.7	9.5
SLSJ-75-45-003	0.07546	32.9	23845	444.3	23533	463.0	23190	526.0	1.5	2.8	12.0	15.5
SLSJ-75-60-001	0.07311	53.8	22554	386.9	22116	423.0	24232	511.0	8.7	6.9	17.2	24.3
SLSJ-75-60-002	0.07476	42.9	23400	416.5	23326	458.0	25342	597.0	8.0	7.7	23.3	30.2
SLSJ-75-60-003	0.07325	50.4	22708	396.0	22582	418.0	23731	458.0	4.8	4.3	8.7	13.5
Avg									7%	12%	17%	19%

Adherend Failure

- Failure observed during validation testing in the adherend, close to the finite element model prediction

Adhesive Failure

Adherend Failure

Summary & Conclusions

- VVUQ approach provided a framework to assess major sources of variability in the test and finite element models
- Variability in the fillet angle was major source of error in the initial models
- Discrete Damage Evolution Model remains highest source of uncertainty
- The surrogate model provided similar accuracy as compared to the finite element model
- Model captured adherend failure, which was then observed during validation testing

Future Work

- Double Lap Shear Joint (DLSJ) – currently running LHS to create surrogate models (4x longer simulation time than SLSJ)
- Investigate SLSJ validation testing DIC to obtain velocity ramp rate for simulation
- Deep dive sub model / coupon testing of Discrete Damage Evolution Model inputs
- Investigate adherend failure

Questions?